
The Impact of Priority Development of Public Consciousness on the Sociocultural Establishing of Modern Society

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Abstract: The purpose, main areas, and ideas of the research study are to demonstrate that the priority development of public consciousness plays a pivotal role in the changes of modern society. The scientific importance of the paper is that it will allow developing existence-related fundamentals of public consciousness modernization. The scientific apprehension of events taking place in the world and in the country will allow people to adapt to changes at work, at home, on holidays, in the means of human interaction. The solution to these problems should make a major contribution to the development of national social philosophy. The practical meaning of the findings is a possibility of elaborating a new special course Modernization of Public Consciousness of the Kazakhstan Society.

Keywords: sociality, culture, modernization, society, consciousness.

1. Introduction

The chosen research theme is justified by the fact that modernization of public consciousness of transition societies, including the Kazakhstan one, was due to the transformation of totalitarianism into democracy, the planned economy into the market economy. These processes of the political reform and economy modernization were supposed to be updated with the beginning of the Third Modernization of Kazakhstan. According to the president of the Republic of Kazakhstan Nazarbayev N.A., it is not enough to be among the top 30 developed nations, it's necessary to follow up these major transformations with the forward-looking modernization of public conscience. It's important to take a step towards the future, to change public conscience to become the single Nation of strong and responsible people (Nazarbayev N.A. 2017). Hence, it follows that the studies of sociocultural changes of society as a material basis for public conscience modernization are one of the most relevant problems of social philosophy for today.

The relevance of the research topic results from the fact that fundamental changes of social, economic, political and cultural institutions of the society took place over the years of Kazakhstan development under conditions of independence and sovereignty. However, their evolution was significantly influenced by such escalating negative phenomena as terrorism, violence, illiteracy, diseases, environmental damage, and international conflicts. Clearly, these destructive phenomena were never supposed to take root in the Kazakhstan society; moreover, they were to be rejected and counteracted.

To overcome these destructive phenomena, according to the Nation Leader, any 21 century-worthy Kazakhstan citizen, as the nation as a whole, needs such factors as computer literacy, second-language skills, cultural openness, a program of cultural and confessional agreement as express conditions. The solution to these problems is possible on the ways of nurturing patriotism, tolerance, high culture, respect for human rights and freedoms.

2. Material and methods

The problems of the features of the research methodology of society in transition became topical following the collapse of the USSR when former Soviet republics set a course for the transformation of totalitarianism into democracy, the planned economy into the market economy. It was the progress of these republics towards establishing the modern (postmodern) society.

The detailed study of the formation of the modern society in the sociocultural context involves the use of a set of classical, non-classical, and post-non-classical methods, principles of research study.

Speaking about classical ones, the stage-formation research method is the most widespread.

Daniel Bell's stage approach and his post industrial society concept can be called a creative development of Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth. In his day, the English scientists distinguished five "stages" in the society

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development:

- 1) traditional society;
- 2) pre-conditions to “take-off”;
- 3) shift stage
- 4) growth stage;
- 5) the period of a high level of mass consumption.

According to him, these stages characterize the stages of traditional society transition into industrial one based on the development of instruments of labor (Rostow W.W 1971).

Karl Marx distinguished bottom-up stages of development from personal dependence through personal independence at thing dependence to free individuality of universally developed man and defined five economic formations of society, correspondingly: 1) tribal, 2) antique, 3) feudal, 4) bourgeois, 5) future communist form of general property (Marx K., Engels F. 1978).

The Karl Marx formation approach allow considering the society structure a system and its stages, which, on the one hand, will be obligatory for each nation, and, on the other hand, each society at each stage will have a similar structure.

In the introduction to *The Coming of Post-Industrial Society*, D. Bell provides the extended criticism for the Karl Marx formation approach to society. He states that his stage approach is inconsistent with the Marx’s formation approach by a number of features (D. Bell, 2004). He states that it is stages and not formations characterize the phases of traditional society transition to the industrial one based on the development of instruments of labour. Bell sees the difference of the post-industrial society from the industrial society (R. Aron) in the development of service economy, research and technology specialists’ domination, the central role of theoretical scientific knowledge as a source of innovations and policy decisions in society, the opportunities of self-maintained technologic growth, the development of new “smart” equipment. Analyzing these new features in the economy, Bell reasoned that the society’s making a transition from the industrial stage of development to the post-industrial stage with a predominance of the service sector in the society instead of the production sector.

When considering his concept, it’s important to take into account the following:

- He forecasted the emergence of a new type of society and didn’t study the established “post-industrial society”;
- The concept of post-industrial society covers advanced economies – USA, Western countries, and Japan.

This concept of post-industrial society was later developed in the works of Z. Brzeziński, J. Galbraith, A. Toffler, and others. In the 1990s, many researchers associated the theory of post-industrial society with the idea of an information society, and sometimes they interpreted these notions as synonyms.

However, the stage-formation approach of K. Marx, R. Aron, W. Rostow, D. Bell and others to the study of sociocultural modernization of society is somewhat limited in historical terms. In this regard, we can agree with Russian scientist Rozov N.S., who states that the strength of this approach is the opportunity to understand universal historical invariants of social evolution, technological and social progress, irreversibility of changes, correlation of development levels. He states that the stage-formation approach weakness is well-known from the critics on the

part of civilizational and humanitarian paradigms’ adherents ... The main and almost generally accepted thesis of this is the following. European history is not the center at all and not a type of movement over the layers of phases (stages, formations) for the remaining parts of world history, but, on the contrary, European history is a very peculiar phenomenon (Rozov N.S. 2000).

It should be recognized the theory of socioeconomic formations is a West European phenomenon, which fails to explain many realias under current conditions and, therefore, doesn’t fulfill its heuristic function.

Firstly, its opponents fairly note that the theory of formations is initially based on the postulates considered to be true without proof. It reads: progress as the main form of movement and formation nature as the main way of progress evolvment; formation as a rigid sequential stage consequence; homogeneity of formation content; material production superiority; production relations as a society basis; “class” – the main unit of society and history subject.

Secondly, none of the named main theoretical points taken as a basis of the formation theory is certain today. The point is the theory of socioeconomic formations is based on the theoretical conclusions of the 21st century. For this reason it fails to explain many current contradictions: simultaneous presence of the areas of progressive development and the areas of underdevelopment, stagnation, and dead-locks; transforming a nation – in one form or another – into an important factor of social production relations; modification of classes; appearance of a new hierarchy of values with a priority of universal human values over the values of classes.

However, it should be also noted that the theory of postindustrial society development has become today the main alternative to the traditional Marxist teaching. Although the opponents of the concept rightly refer to the incapacity of technological determinism and a somewhat utopian nature of many researchers’ views (Inozemtsev V.L. 2001).

The civilizational approach (Oswald Spengler, Arnold Toynbee, Slavophiles, Eurasians) is the antithesis of the stage-formation approach based on the production and economic relations development. The civilizational approach is based on the change of sociocultural types of relations.

Thus, using the apriori-culturological method of society’s socio-political transformation research Spengler skeptically interprets the decay of the newest European culture and its philosophical apprehension. He didn’t share the traditional approach to the periodization of Europe’s history into antiquity, Middle Ages, etc. He names this history division a meaningless “European-centrist Ptolemean system” since, according to him, the humankind history actually consists of a set of cultures independent of each other. In his opinion, world history is the general biography of cultures, which successively goes through the stages of birth, development, maturity, old age, and death.

Drawing the line between the notions of culture and civilization, Oswald Spengler states that culture consists of the groups of people with the common perception of “nation” with the clear impact of immanent state idea. According to him, the “high” culture is characterized at the early period by the presence of nobles and the clergy. Its first stage (feudality) is determined by peasants’ spirit, the

second stage is characterized by a transition of a feudal union to an estate state, the final stage is marked by the maturing state idea and states' formation. According to Oswald Spengler, culture turns into civilization going through the stages of historic ascension. The advent of civilization in big cities is followed by the social structuring of the formless masses of "the fourth estate". Then, democratic and totalitarian forms of socio-political organization of society are built, which eventually degenerate into mastery and caesarism. Towards the end of civilization, according to Oswald Spengler, the organism of nation's turns into an amorphous mass and, collapsing, becomes a "prey" of other nations. This takes nations back to a state of early existence, alienation from the world (Spengler O. 1994).

To some extent, the words of Frank S.L. explain this idea: Slavophiles and Spengler detected distinction and even opposition between spiritual creativity, depth, and intensity of the spiritual life itself in the difference between civilization and culture, on the one hand, and gaining of external might, dead tools, on the other hand (Bubbayer F.S. 2001).

Danilevsky N.Y. develops the organic theory of shut down culture-historical types and, therefore, split the humankind's unity for ever. This theory suggests an idea that national culture develops immanently and is interrelated to other cultures. At the same time, the development of national culture, according to his theory, should take place on its own base avoiding a strong impact on the part of other culture or else remaking its achievements in a creative manner. Subject to the conditions, a powerful cultural tradition unique in its originality can be established (Danilevsky N.Y. 2002).

The theory of cultures' numerosity and heterogeneity suggests rejecting the Eurocentric idea of culture-historical progress. It rules out the substitution of one culture with the other. This Danilevsky's theory demonstrates the danger of imposing so-called "universal human values" since values are always of a specific-historical nature. In this case, he uses the term of universal human values in terms of western society's values.

This cultural polyphonism, geopolitical position of Russia predetermines its peculiar historical path. In this respect, Trubetskoy N.S. notes that Russian culture always has to search for in all directions, expend energy in coordinating these elements of heterogeneous cultures, nose for matching elements from the mass of values of two cultures. According to the Eurasian concept, the task of true culture-historical self-cognition consists in the cognition of yourself, your identity. In his opinion, only genuine self-cognition will show the man (or his nation) his real place in the world. He states that only sufficiently original ethnic culture is genuine and it is the only one that meets ethical, aesthetic, and practical requirements placed by any culture (Trubetskoy N.S. 1995).

Developing the Trubetskoy's methodology, Savitsky P.N. proclaims the existence of a specific Eurasian-Russian culture and its specific subject as a symphonic personality. He considers that dim cultural self-consciousness the Slavophiles had is already not enough, although "we honour them as most kindred. However, we reject flatly the essence of Westernism, i.e. rejection of identity and, eventually, the very existence of our culture. We feel

ashamed for Russian people who have to get know about the existence of Russian culture from German Spengler". Excluding the cunning attempts of Western spirit infected Slavophiles too, to dissolve the problem of Eurasian-Russian culture in a dim teaching of tribal kindred, Savitsky P.N. had to put a polemical emphasis on "Turan elements" and he, abandoning the supposedly scientific mechanical approach to the problem, sets forth unity and wholeness of culture, its personal quality. He believes that culture is born and develops as an organic whole, that's why it's immediately ("convergently") manifested in the political and socioeconomic forms, lifestyle, ethnic type, and in the geographic features of its territory (Savitsky P.N. 1997).

Gumilyev L.N. develops and carries to a logical completion the general-Eurasian idea that ethnically Great Russians (velikorossy), the Russians aren't just a branch of East Slavs but also a particular ethnos on the basis of Turkic-Slavic merger. Based on this, he considers that the Great Russian civilization was built based on the Turkic-Slavic ethnogenesis, a union of Forest and Steppe, the combination of which composes the historic essence of Russia, predetermining the nature of its culture, civilization, ideology, political destiny.

After Spengler and Toynbee, he distinguishes the cycles of civilizations and cultures, as well as corresponding ethnoses. In his point of view, the ethnocultural formations of nation, state, religious communities are similar to living organisms. They pass the stages of birth, youth, maturity, and aging, and then disappear or turn into so-called "relicts".

This is fundamentally new that the last Eurasian considers the development of society as establishing of a social-natural entirety against which the adequate understanding of a specifically culture-historical place of each nation is possible. He introduces the term of "place-development" regarding the study of culture-historical development of some or another country. He considers that Eurasia is an adequate "place-development", fertile richest ground for ethnogenesis and culture genesis. In this respect, Gumilyev L.N. rightly notes: "A distinctive feature of eurasianism in a general and ideocratic state, in particular, is interconnection and interdependence of all theoretical elements. The entirety of the peoples lively conscious of "the community of cultural and historical traditions", keeps the self-sufficient economy at certain place-development". Therefore, we need to consider world history not in the unipolar version "West and the rest", but in a many-polar, besides, North and East Eurasia is of particular interest since they're an alternative to the West source of important planet civilizational processes (Gumilyev L.N. 2001).

The socio-dynamic approach of Sorokin P. can be referred to non-classical research methods of sociocultural phenomena. He carried out a detailed analysis of the generic structure of socio-political phenomena. It allowed him to understand the society as a unity of sociality and politics, the formed and the transformed in the course of human life activity. Explaining his idea, Sorokin P. notes that the structure of sociocultural interaction has three inseparable aspects: 1) personality as an interaction subject; 2) society as an entirety of interacting individuals with its socio-cultural relations and processes; and 3) culture as a totality of meanings, values, and norms the individuals

have and the totality of carriers who objectify, socialize, and reveal these meanings... None of these members of inseparable trine (personality, society, and culture) can exist without two others". Putting an emphasis on the interaction as a generic model of sociocultural phenomena, Pitirim Sorokin notes the continuous changeability of historical process. In his opinion, certain forms of social organization continuously appear in society: certain forms of production, family forms, political system. They live, they develop and, eventually, are replaced with new ones (Sorokin P. 1994).

The socio-political approach of Durkheim is very much in line with the Sorokin's approach. He directs the analysis of society's sociocultural changes to specific forms of social organization, which characterize the shifts from mechanical solidarity (by similarities) to the organic solidarity of people. His teaching of "collective consciousness" based on organic solidarity is related to a problem of "collective unconscious" known from psychoanalysis. In the works of J. Herder and German romantics, and history showed up in Hegel's philosophy, the founders of ethnopsychology tried to see in the "spirit" the fullest implementation of organic solidarity, which, according to them, is "people". The studies of the science about society drastically changed the ideas of the reality of, conditionally speaking, "collective consciousness" established in the Romantic school. After his predecessors – ethnopsychologists – regarding this issue, Durkheim admitted this specific reality, understanding "collective consciousness" as a "set of beliefs and feelings averagely common for the members of one and the same society", which forms a certain system with its own life". However, as distinct from ethnopsychologists, Durkheim considers the fact of "collective" (or "common") consciousness an indicator of not highest over individual synthesis but a certain "type" of *socium* typical for archaic stages of its evolution. Taking the indicator of "solidarity" as a basis of his classification of social development phases, French scientist opposed, as we know, archaic *socii*, united by "mechanical solidarity", and modern societies, which differ with "organic solidarity" determined by the phenomenon of labour differentiation.

It may happen that translating the synchronous (ideal-typical) matrix of traditional *socium* features, outlined by Durkheim E., into a diachronous perspective of historical process will raise doubts of methodologic nature. Opponents could ask how much this procedure is rightful. This objection can be answered in two ways. On the one hand, with an obvious truism, pointing that heuristic potential of any innovative concept is not solely measured by the area of specific implications made by its author. A French scientist indicated this regarding the question under consideration (Aron R. 1993). He believed that Durkheim considered it possible to locate different known societies on a line according to the complexity level starting with one-segment to polysegment ones of double complexity. This theory appears very important not in the context of Durkheim's sociology but as a project of some completed form of social science". On the other hand, it's possible to prove the relevance of the Durkheim matrix for socio-cultural transformation analysis. To this end, it's necessary to decisively demonstrate the interrelation of basis components of social archaics with internal (system)

determinants of history. The appeal to psychoanalysis in respect to modernization issue and related problem of national-cultural identity is inevitable for two reasons: the stronger state of consciousness, the stronger it resists anything that could weaken it; the more it definite, the less room for changes. So, one could foresee the progress of differentiation of labour will be slower and more difficult, the more powerful and definite common consciousness is. According to him, "specialization is not the only possible outcome in the struggle for existence" (Durkheim E. 1991).

The use of David Durkheim's social-science theories makes it possible to study sociopolitical transformations of transition society and changes in the citizens' public conscience interrelated, as well as the ideology and Utopia elements presented in their conscience.

The structural-functional approach of Parsons T. can be considered a post-non-classical method of studying changes of a sociocultural nature. Based on the structural-functional approach, he considered structural changes of society a progressive evolution towards higher system levels, which express the value of freedom, the rationalization of historical process. According to the American sociologist, such groups of processes the liberalization consists of can be distinguished. He includes the process of differentiation of main societal-functional structures into there groups as relatively independent: life-supporting (economy), spiritually-integrating (culture), status-differentiating (social structure), power-regulating (politics). Moreover, this researcher includes into this group the emergence and inclusion of new components ensuring the transforming system's integration into it: adoption of norms of civil society or more precisely societal community (rights and liabilities of each citizen, ensuring the involvement of citizens in the formation of government institutions, etc.). It also includes the establishing of the market system, production industrialization, rationalization of administration's organizational structures (growth in bureaucracy); appearance and legitimization of political parties, professional unions and other forms of citizens' mass self-organization. According to him, liberalization should express growing in the system of new components disintegrating it on new grounds. This is a deep alienation of the person from life and labour conditions, globalization of politico-military oppositions between different types of society, including the danger of humankind self-destruction, the growth of environmental hazards, environment degradation (Parsons, T., 1961).

All these classical and non-classical, post-non-classical methods and theories can be included in the toolkit of sociocultural approach. It involves the understanding of society as a unity of sociality and culture created as a result of human activity. There are more than enough evidence in support of this statement. Thus, culture is joint spiritual experience of the humankind. Everything created by the human falls within the culture notion content. As a human activity product, culture is its secondary, artificial environment of life activity, i.e. a non-organic body of the organic human. This environment is composed of language, value system, traditions, beliefs, customs, social psychology, people's mindset, and social organization of life. The inextricable connection to life indicates a social nature of culture. The social nature of culture is determined

by the fact that the latter is created and changed by people in the course of usage. Culture always expresses accumulation, succession, and generalization of social experience of humankind life. In this regard, culture is a way of socium existence, a public good, which people inherits and propagates. In turn, social life is of a culturological nature. Social relations have cultural content. The world of culture is a world of values. Values are what is important and holy to the man and social communities. They, like spiritual clamps, foundations, and landmarks, help people withstand life difficulties, allow aligning social reality and give meaning to the human life. Values are eventually devoted to the human's and socium's benefit. It means that culture appears as content and goal of the historical process, as a unity of public conscience forms, ways of human activity, a means of human establishing and development.

In other words, the sociopolitical approach provides an understanding of society as a unity of sociality and politics created in the course of human activity. Sociality — a totality of relations of each person or another social subject with other subjects— economic, social, ideological, political relationships formed in the activity processes.

The specific nature of the sociopolitical approach is that it takes into account such aspects of human existence, as a type of human and society correlation, a nature of culture, a type of sociality. They're all interrelated and interinfluence as major components of human communities.

The socio-political approach doesn't oppose other approaches but integrates them. It unites civilizational, formational, socio-dynamic, sociological methods into a single unity. The civilizational approach as the most extensive captures stable components of the human history (anthropologic, ethnic, cultural). The formational approach focuses attention on more changeable (social, personal) structures. The sociological approach indicates the diachronic moments of the historical process. By synthesizing them, the sociocultural approach reveals the relation of the stable and the changeable in the relationship of the personality and society, culture, and sociality. The socio-political approach can be made specific in the form of a few principles, which help to shape an image of society as an integral sociocultural system and clearer comprehend the problems of socio-cultural transformation. They can be schematically expressed in the following principles.

The action-related principle of philosophy with respect to socio-cultural phenomena in a particular form acts as a principle of active man. As a basic principle, it focuses attention on biological, social and cultural aspects of the man and on the elements of his structure as an action subject. At the same time, the very action of the subject is understood as a component of interaction with other subjects, material to them and fulfilling certain functions regarding all subjects of interaction. Thus, the principle of *Homo activus* is also the principle of human interaction as the simplest sociocultural phenomenon.

The principle of politics and sociality interpenetration indicates the presence of these two dimensions in any society. It suggests the constant interrelation and mutual influence of these two dimensions, which aren't reduced to and aren't derived from each other.

The principle of anthroposocietal correspondence

allows revealing the compatibility of personal-behavioral characteristics of the human as a member of the given society and the remaining characteristics of this society, in particular, the unity of culture and sociality.

These are the sectors of society where compatibility between people should be achieved. This principle indicates that in a "traditionalistic society", the characteristics of the human should correspond to established societal structures. They limit or shut the social field of the activity of people who violate traditions. In a "liberal or modern society," he extends the field of people's activities for changing established but no any longer corresponding their heightened needs and capacities.

The principle of socio-cultural balance suggests equilibrium between cultural and social components as a condition of society's stability. It means that functions, structures, and processes of society should be aimed at providing the balanced meeting of conflicting needs, values, and interests of actors.

The principle of symmetry and mutual reversibility as a form of manifesting the philosophical principle of rejecting societal processes indicates that each process expressing the dynamics of society as an integral system has a specific direction. An oppositely directed (symmetrical, paired) process corresponds to its reflection. It means that when a process shifts from one stage to other it can become the opposite. In this case, the integration transits into reintegration and back; and symmetrical twoness of processes is of a functional nature. In other words, one of the paired processes ensures the reproduction of corresponding structures, and the other gives rise to their change in society (Lapin N.I., 2000).

Based on these principles, one can consider society a large self-sufficient sociocultural system, which appears and changes as a result of interaction of active subjects of transformation. Functions and structures of sociocultural system ensure the balanced meeting of numerous needs, values, and interests of the actor, their dynamic balance is implemented through the aggregate of societal processes. The type of society is determined by a type of anthroposocietal correspondence, and structure and dynamics are determined by the parameters of sociocultural balance, by the predominance of reproducing (traditional) or changing (innovative) processes. Sociocultural changes of society, therefore, take place as needs grow and capacities of transformation subjects develop.

Thus, based on the above-mentioned methods and principles it can be found out that the formation of the economic and social basis for establishing an open democratic society started at the initial stage of sociocultural modernization.

3. Literature review

The modernization of public conscience is a reflection of socio-cultural modernization of social existence. In this case, sociocultural changes (modernization) is the initial object of research. In scientific literature of the last decades, the "sociocultural changes" category is often substituted with the "modernization" notion. However, the polysemy of this notion makes its correct definition difficult.

The “modernization” notion means some options of culture and society transformation. In other words, the notions of modernization and transformation make the content of the category of sociocultural changes of a transition society specific. The ever-growing use of these notions, in particular, modernization, predetermined the need for elaborating the main postulates of its recognized, classical interpretation.

Polish scientist Sztompka P. is considered one of the recognized authorities in this area. He rightly states that modernization in a broad sense expresses all progressive social changes in society when socium moves forward in accordance with the accepted scale of improvements. According to him, it also reflects a complex of social, political, economic, cultural and intellectual transformations, which appeared in the West in the 16th century and reached their climax in the 20th century, contributing to the modern society formation. In a narrow sense, this notion reflects the efforts of backward or underdeveloped societies, which seek to move from the periphery to the center of modern societies. For some or other development scenarios, the subject was initially placed outside the social system (God, the Absolute idea...), then it was placed inside a social organism, but in an unhumanized manner, as its own organism developmental potency, then it was personified in Great man, Historical character. The next major step – the appeal to a collective subject. At this point, Sztompka P. distinguishes two paradigms: the logic of collective action and the logic of individual interrelations, forming complex networks. According to his theory, the actor is manifested in the diversity of his modes, including the acts of his collective creation in the form of sub-individual social structures. Following this (or similar) logic of reasoning, he covers, in summary, the search logic of great thinkers of the past and, at the same time, becomes a participator of the creative process of today’s theoreticians. Generally speaking, he understands social changes as any irreversible change of social system considered as unity (Sztompka P. 1996).

American scientist Robert Nisbet considers that the development of Western civilization takes place by both knowledge accumulation and the process of generating material wealth. Initially, the progress of society development is based on the linear idea of history typical of Judaic-Christian religious tradition. Since the 18th century, according to him, the idea of progress started separating from religious origins and the notions of progress and science started fusing. He considers this process was accompanied by threatening events: while the progress was initially interpreted as increased human freedom, starting with the second half of the 19th century an understanding appeared of the progress as an increase in “controllability” – simply put, expanding the authority of abstract state over the man and environment (Nisbet Robert Alexander, 2007).

Another American scientist Tilly Charles states that social movements start developing as means of mobilization of group resources when people lack institutional forms of expression of their opinion or when authorities impose direct repressions. The typical forms of collective action and revolt, in his opinion, change depending on historical and cultural circumstances (Tilly Charles, 2004).

The founder of the world-systems theory, a repre-

sentative of Neo-Marxism, Immanuel Wallerstein believes that it’s necessary to rethink the social science of the 19th century since its numerous prerequisites are still deeply rooted in people’s minds. Once it was considered they set their spirit free, today they are the main intellectual barrier for the objective analysis of social world, which should be free from considerations of faith, the misbelief that the inevitable triumph of goodwill is waiting for us (Wallerstein, Immanuel. 1997).

American scientist Walter Buckley advanced the basic theory of sociocultural process based on the principle of activity. It allows revealing the structural-functional model of a self-regulating, homeostatic system penetrated with negative, compensatory backward linkages. He complemented this model with a model of “morphogenetic system” with positive, supportive backward linkages, where structures are continuously built and transformed. Buckley believes that his morphogenetic system “emerges”, “becomes built-in”, “generates, produces and restructures itself”. It demonstrated some automatism, as well as the rigid quality of the system itself (Buckley, Walter. 1967).

The theory of active society of American sociologist and politologist Amitai Etzioni is much in line with the Buckley’s theory to a certain degree. He tried to develop such scheme of society reorganization where universal human values would be implemented in the best way. The key parameters of this society – responsivity (sensitivity of the ruling leadership to the needs of the members of the lowest steps of social ladder) and authenticity (authenticity of the human needs themselves common for all the members of society regardless of their cultural background). One of the ways to increase the industrial society’s activity is strengthening the centralized control over the system operation. Etzioni, speaking of control, means not regulatory control, but the complex interaction of authority and information. In his later works, he pays a lot of attention to the considerations of specific social problems and, in particular, the creation of the system of social indicators enabling the identification and solution to these problems (Etzioni, Amitai 1968a). Later, he complements the system of social indicators with mobilization forces of collectives and communities – as the main source of their own transformations and transformations of their relations with other social units. According to him, this complement allows understanding that a social unit in the course of mobilization is tending to change its own structure and borders, as well as the structure of the higher unit it doesn’t belong to” (Etzioni, Amitai 1968b).

Thus, Etzioni shows that the human society is a “macroscopic and continuous social movement” included in the “intense and continuous self-transformation”. The ultimate driver is found in “self-triggering transformability” and an ability to creatively respond to impacts. The center of this ability is collectives, groups, and social organizations; the mechanism is identified with collective action, largely within the political process. The theory of social dimension brings up a question: “how an actor directs the process and changes the structure or borders of social unity”? It also poses a question how this structure was modeled, how it was maintained, how it can be changed, where the sources of driving forces are located,

who concentrates knowledge and who is capable of fulfillment. Etzioni considers the actions of social self-transformation in various types of collectives genuine subjects.

French scientists took an active part in the development of the problem of public conscience modernization. Well-known structuralist Alain Touraine harshly criticizes the materialist conception of history from the perspective of “self-producing community” (Touraine, Alain 1977). Based on this position, Touraine also criticizes the development theory and the structuralism theory, which “conform the feeling of collective action to inevitable laws or requirements of historical reality”. They, therefore, take the subject out of the sociological perspective, they consider it a simple emanation of the system. His evolutionistic, or historical, concept appeals to comparative history or even to history philosophy. According to it, societies follow each other on the way of progress, rationality, and strengthening of the national state. The cause of action is a positive or negative activity of the very social doers. He, therefore, shows that the man is a history maker, and society is nothing more than an unstable and, probably, an incoordinate result of social relations and social clashes.

Together with Polish, American, French, the problem of society modernization was intensively developed by British scientists. For example, Anthony Giddens developed the theory of structuration (Giddens, Anthony. 1991a), where he dissociates himself from all the theories typical of “orthodox consensus” involving the materialization of social integrities and social determinism of doers. Combining this critics of functionalism and structuralism from the perspective of “understanding, or interpretative, sociology”, Giddens denies the notion of the very structure.

Focusing attention on the ever-changing nature of social reality, which true ontological substrate lies in the action and interactions of people, he believes that life is happening being transformed and its main content is continuous production and reproduction of society. It supposes structuring of a social system means within the framework of general rules and resources. In this case, structural features of systems are both a means and the result of practice, in the course of which system data are formed”. The system is formed in the course of subjects’ – people’s actions and interaction (Giddens, Anthony 1991b).

The other part of the “activity-structure” equation is derived by Tom R. Burns and Helena Flam in the theory of social rule (Burns, Tom R. and Flam, H. 1987). Despite the fact that the authors, as they state, aim to “bridge structure and actor levels”, they put an emphasis not on actors, who form, but on structures that are being formed. They consider the latter in the normative terms as complex networks of rules. According to them, human activity – taking into account its diversity and originality – is organized and mainly managed by socially determined rules, as well as rule systems. They develop the ideas of normative ontology of the social world developed by Torgny Segerstedt. He stated that each type of interaction and cooperation should involve general norms. Only with general norms and generally valid symbols, we can forecast (Segerstedt, Torgny T. 1966: 12).

The main area of this theory is a complex analysis of

social rules, which compose the “deep structures of human history”. They are divided into three types of “modules”: rule system, rule mode, and grammar. The rule systems include rules “depending on the context and being of a temporal specific nature, – rules used for structuring and regulating social interactions, implementing activities, specific tasks or interaction in socially conditioned forms”. The modes of rules are maintained by social sanctions, authority, and control networks and, therefore, gain an objective, external nature in the human’s eye. They’re close to what is usually called instructions (in the normative sense of this general category). On the individual level, the system turns into “the grammar of social actions” used to structure and regulate interactions with each other in certain situations.

Margaret Archer harshly criticizes the Giddens’s theory of structuring, complementing it with the morphogenesis theory. The main advantage of the morphogenetic perspective is the realization of the fact that “the ability of social systems to be subject to major restructuring – eventually due to the human – is a unique feature, which differs them from organic or mechanical systems” (Archer, Margaret S. 1985: 59).

The central notion of morphogenesis refers to the mutual influence of structures and actions, which occurs in the given form, structure or in the given state of the system. When studying these mutual influences it’s necessary to apply the principle of “analytical” and not “conceptual duality”. According to the former, in the course of analysis, actions and structures are being separated since the emergent properties of sociocultural systems involve discontinuity between the initial interaction and their final product. In contrast, the principle of duality could involve the loss of “central conflation” - elision (connection) of two elements, losing autonomy from each other or independence of one of them or both at once.

The representative of modern historical sociology Norbert Elias criticizes his colleagues for the uncritical compilation of facts at the level of empiric study. Elias set the processual perspective against this drawback expressed in abstracting from temporal and dynamic parameters of human society organization. It means the realization of what the immediate present sociologists consider is only a negligible instantaneous phase in the flow of human development and that this flow, based on the past, crosses the present and heads for the possible future. Societies are considered in historical time. It is due to the fact that each modern society is grown from previous societies and goes beyond its borders turning into various possible future societies (Elias, Norbert 1987: 226).

This process is mainly unplanned, although it includes shorter or longer episodes of planned, intended social change. Changes aren’t of an automatic or inevitable nature; the process is completely determined by people in their complex interaction, interdependence, which Elias called figurations. Their nodes are individual doers, as well as groups and even states. Figurations form a flexible grid structure of tensions, an unstable tense balance, a balance of forces moving back and forth, outweighing first one side and then another. These webs or networks of interhuman relations with authorities as the main relation (uniting people but opposing them as well; giving rise to not only their cooperation but conflicts as well) are internally fluid,

unstable, subject to all kinds of changes. These are models of movement of greater or lesser length. In these figurations, people concentrate their own history-changing activities.

Philip Abrams states the need for complete integration of sociology and history. In his opinion, the only strong method to create sociology is the historical one. There are ontological causes for this since sociologists and historians deal with the same “crazy non-mechanical machine”, - human society. Both statistical and traditional approaches proposing “the laws and stages of evolution and development where the need for the very laws is stated” appeared completely inadequate. In his view of history and sociology, the interrelation between them can't help but exist because they share the same main subject matter. They are both try to understand the mystery of human action, they are both try to do it using the terms of social structuring processes.

The idea of process helps to bridge the traditionally opposed statics and dynamics, as well as the structure and the action. The division into diachrony and synchrony is absurd. Sociologists should deal with eventfulness because that's the way structuring takes place. The sociology of process should provide an alternative to outdated sociological action theories and system theories because the process is a relation between action and structure. Thus, society should be understood as a process, historically created by individuals who are created historically by society. This process is endless, consistent and cumulative; actions are taken at each its stage under conditions, which were established in the past, and, these actions, in turn, prepare circumstances for the future. This positive long-lasting process of structuring is the central subject of sociological analysis (Abrams, Philip 1982).

4. Results

- The review of the West literature regarding sociocultural changes of society in the context of social consciousness modernization contributed to the following results:

- irreversible progressive social changes of society on the accepted scale of improvements, the subject of which gradually becomes a part of the system within the paradigm of collective action and logics of individual interrelations;
- linear social changes of society associated with progress and science, restriction of human freedom, strengthening of state power over the man and environment;
- development of social changes in society under the influence of collective actions and objections in the context of various historical and cultural conditions;
- development of social world under secularization, coping misconception and triumph of goodwill;
- sociocultural changes of society take place under activities, structural-functional self-regulation, morpho-genetic structuring;
- sociocultural changes of society under the influence of response to true needs of people, mobilization of collective's and society's forces to have an impact on their decision;
- sociocultural changes of society are the impact of

people's activity, the result of social relations and social conflicts;

- sociocultural changes of society are the result of using common rules and resources and unintended results in the process of interaction.

The polysemy of this notion makes it difficult to provide its correct definition. Nonetheless, we should understand “modernization” as some options of transformation of culture and society. In other words, the notions of modernization and transformation make the content of the transition society's sociocultural changes category specific. The ever-growing use of these notions, in particular, modernization, predetermined the need for elaborating the main postulates of its classical interpretation.

The classical interpretation of the modernization notion allows identifying the most common characteristics of the breakdown of traditional society with its consciousness and transformation into the modern one.

These characteristics form the basis of the process of modern open society formation. In the course of this process, market economy, private property, industries are formed in the field of economy. In the social context, the urbanized class society is being established in the course of changes. In the field of culture, changes cause secularization of social consciousness, develop mass education and science.

The practice of sociocultural changes in Kazakhstan, Russia, which is widely discussed in the scientific literature, is of interest for efficient development of the issue. Quite a profound comparative analysis of social-economic reforms of Kazakhstan and Russia are carried out in a number of works (Nechiporenko O.V., Nysanbaev A.N., 2005) to clarify the specific features of social consciousness modernization under the influence and sociocultural factors in modernizational processes of the Kazakhstan society ... the issues of evaluations, opinions and perceptions of subelites on the beginning of tradition and innovation, identity and universality in its development (Ermakhanova S.A. 2006).

It's possible to agree with Zdravomyslov A.G., who distinguishes three concepts in the literature, covering modernization paths: a) crisis as a manifestation of isolation (N.I. Lapin; b) systemic crisis of society (T.I. Zaslavskaya); c) “high categorial crisis” (Y.A. Levada). He considers both advantages and disadvantages of each of them. Together they could be characterized as modernizational theories, which overcome common judgments on the crisis nature, interpret the specific nature of each stage and are aimed at studying fundamental conflicts that weren't covered in the framework of the Soviet socio-political system (Zdravomyslov A.G., 2007).

The researchers' development of the conceptual framework makes it possible to reveal the features of modern social changes in various regions of the world. For example, N.I. Lapin proposed to consider modernization in the 3-dimensional temporal perspective. Firstly, as a secular process triggered by industrial revolution, in the course of which a small group of modernized societies has been developed today. Secondly, as a diversified process, in the course of which backward countries catch up more advanced ones. Thirdly, as attempts of modernized nations to meet new challenges on the way of innovations and

reforms. Furthermore, the transformation problems of post-Soviet countries at the end of the 80s of the previous century gave a new impetus to the discussions on the vector and nature of modernization direction (Lapin N.I. 2015). This is particularly true for the transformation of the very type of sociocultural system as a transition from one type of anthropo-societal correspondence to the other, i.e. transformations of traditional society into the modern one. This historical process is implemented by many generations and lasts for decades.

Depending on the context and purposes of a study, one could use the notions of transformation and modernization in the above-mentioned senses since all their diverse shades are captured in the stated definitions. In these meanings, the notions of transformation and modernization reflect various moments, the aspects of the globalizing democratic transit of the world community.

The scientific literature understands the modern society as all societies existing from the beginning of modern history. The word “modern” (French modern – present-day, contemporary) was first used in the 5th century to distinguish the “Christian present” granted the official status and the “pagan Roman past”. Since then “modernity” (belonging to the modern age) always implied the need for epoch’s realization to relate itself with the antiquity when comprehending itself. In any epoch there were periods of transition from the old to the new, that’s why countries called themselves “new”, modern from the days of Charlemagne and the Enlightenment.

Traditional society is understood as a society regulated by traditions. The preservation of traditions is much greater value than changes, development. For example, the social order in Eastern countries is characterized by rigid class hierarchy and stable social communities, a special method of social life regulation, strict observance of traditions and customs. This society’s organization is preserved as it is and protects sociocultural foundations of life.

The traditional man perceives the world and established order of life as something integrated whole, not subject to change. In doing so, the person’s role in the society and his status are also defined by tradition.

In this society, collective mindsets prevail, individualism is discouraged since the freedom of individual actions can break the established routine. In other words, we have here the primacy of collective interests over private ones, including the primacy of interests of existing hierarchy structures (state, clan, etc.). That’s why not so much individual efficiency as a place in hierarchy (administrative, class, clan, etc.) a person holds is recognized in traditional society.

Traditional societies are authoritarian. Authoritarianism at this point is necessary, in particular, to suppress tradition violation or its change. In the economic field of these societies, redistribution relations, as opposed to market exchange, are dominant, and the market economy elements are strictly regulated. These measures are against the increase in social mobility by means of free market relations and the change of the social structure of society.

Clearly, the modification of traditional society took place hyperslow, almost invisible to the individual. At the same time, the periods of accelerated growth took place in traditional societies as well, in particular, in the territory of Eurasia in the 1st millennium B.C. However, even these

“accelerations” of history were carried out slowly in terms of the modern standards, and upon their completions, the society again returned to a static state with a predominance of cyclical behavior.

Shifting from the model of traditional society was largely determined by trade development. This was the case in ancient Rome up to 3rd century B.C., England, and Holland of the 16th-17th centuries. However, the ultimate – rapid and irreversible – transformation of traditional society has been taking place only from the 18th century in the period of industrial revolution. And now this process covers almost the entire world.

Nonetheless, traditional societies are associated in mass consciousness with East and modern ones with West. These associations reflect nations’ mindset and have a specific historical-geographical meaning. They characterize a particular type of civilization, i.e. a particular system and way of living, the peculiarity of economic and political organization, features of ideology, culture, standards of ethics, aesthetic values.

Ecological, demographic, technological, economic, political, sociocultural, social-psychological changes take place in different spheres of life. They’re different in rate, scale, complexity, and direction. And these sociocultural changes are due to the transformations of main social institutions of society. In turn, the change of social institutions helps to find out the causes and factors of sociocultural changes, immediate and long-run prospects of outlined trends, a stage nature of the dynamic process, and many other tendencies in the socium’s life.

For example, the predominance of agricultural practice in economy, stability of social structure, the significant impact of religious teachings on the life’s class organization, the primacy of collectivism over individualism, authoritarianism in the system of authorities’ relations, people’s passivity and paternalism are typical of traditional society.

The classical interpretation of the modernization notion allows revealing the general characteristics of traditional society breakdown with its consciousness and transformation into the modern one.

These characteristics can be as follows:

- revolutionism, which results from the fundamentality of differences between traditional and modern societies;
- complexity as an impossibility of reducing this process to one factor or aspect;
- consistency suggesting the interdependence of factors in the course of changes;
- globality since the process currently covers all countries and nations to a greater or lesser degree;
- length measured not by decades, but several centuries;
- stageness as an opportunity of distinguishing levels or modernization phases;
- homogeneity of results, in which a tendency to social unification of societies in the process of modernization is reflected;
- irreversibility as the impossibility of returning to the previous phase, while there’s room for failures and temporary backdowns in the process of modernization;
- progressiveness, despite deep sacrifices and disturbances in the course of modernization, its results are desirable due to industrial society’s decisive superiority over the agrarian one (Borodkin L.I., Kvasova E.A. 2001).

These postulates make up the content of the process of the modern open society formation. The market economy, private property, industries are being formed in the course of this process in the economic field.

These traditionalistic features in society appear regulatory prescriptions, basic attitudes. They accumulate social and spiritual values, the previous experience of generations, the people's social-historical memory. Being the basis of sociocultural identification, traditional values are guidelines for many generations, they shape the people's historical memory as an idea of the community of historic destinies, the historic past as a stable component of national identity (Rassadina T.A. 2004).

Values, experience, and memory are transferred through social information in the course of people's activity on the reproduction and development of social relations, culture as a whole. In the course of this activity, the relation between the individual and public consciousness is implemented. In doing so, the spiritual culture penetrates all the social "pores" of society and has an impact on the self-identity of both personality and people.

The person's individual life and his personal identity depend on the collective identity or identities he belongs to. We can speak of national, ethnic, state, cultural, professional, confessional identities. According to Trufanova E.O., the issues of the self-identity of people, nation, state are always acute, and this is particularly relevant today for post-Soviet countries, including Russia. In her opinion, former Soviet republics, for the most part, are still experiencing the "crisis of collective identity" caused by the collapse of the USSR and the need for finding new grounds for their community (Trufanova E.O. 2010). We agree with her that national and cultural identifications make the corner-stone since the nation appeals to the depths of its history, reshapes the national identity.

These searches for identity fairly maintain the integrity and stability of social-historic communities under conditions of the fast-paced world. The integrity of communities triggers the creative innovative activity of its representatives. Traditions as basic elements of culture contribute to the process of sociocultural identity, which is regulated by public opinion based on ethical standards. The notion of "traditional" is also used to denote entire societies where changes take place slowly and step by step.

Thus, traditional values have a great impact on the people's world view. Traditionalism appears as a world view, which "covers public heritage only on the basis that it is heritage and as it is doesn't require further explanations or grounding. Traditionalism protects the heritage of the past from changes". Traditionalism represents such a world view that the social group's heritage transforms into a positive tradition. Its adherents have no doubt about the very authority of history. The past is a value, memory's and imitation's object for them. They see the role of the present in the steadfast adherence to the ideas and causes of the previous generations. At the same time, one shouldn't interpret traditionalism as a rigid, uncompromising opposition to progress, innovations. Traditionalism is a notion of the same order conservatism is. Indeed, it doesn't come to the west

culture representatives' mind to criticize conservatism as an entirely negative phenomenon (Shatsky E.1995). Traditionalism, which dates back to the end of the 18th – the beginning of the 19th centuries, cannot be considered an exceptionally anti-revolutionary ideology. It's known that apart from purely economic and political interests traditionalism always expressed (and expresses) the hopes of significant social sectors for identification of universal sense of the world whole, which would relate the individual to the ideal order similar to that existed in the days of the Golden Age or a specific state. As such, the ideology of traditionalism comprises an essential part of the cultural heritage of all nations. It is manifested in different historic periods more or less depending on a political situation in polemics with liberalism.

Fyodorova M.M. states that "in a nut shell, liberalism was a certain gap from classical political-philosophical traditions, a departure from the political thought developed in antiquity by Plato, Aristotle, and later integrated by Christianity. A free individual equal to all other individuals by his rights – this is the basis of a liberal project; this individual using the most powerful instrument that nature gave him – mind – can create a just society upon the terms of equality of everyone before the law and respect for each other's rights. The first and much later (as ones in Russia) attempts to put this doctrine into practice showed that society is not "transparent" in all its aspects and not resistant to mind, that it has hidden mechanisms, which can distort the principles of equality and justice, that freedom turns into the tough tyranny of the majority. Traditionalism chose a different course: when developing its society model it relied on the classical tradition, on the critics liberalism is based on". Criticizing traditionalism, neoliberalism also persuades West and Russian citizens of that the essence of every person is nothing more than the pursuit of maximum satisfaction at minimum expenses. The problems of morality, sociality, and solidarity are, therefore, left behind. This understanding of neoliberalism becomes increasingly widespread, i.e. the process of its internalization is taking place (Fyodorova M.M. 1997).

Within the dialectic approach, the development of traditional societies should be considered a process accompanied by the change of public conscience's axiological components, perception, and adoption of innovations. In this process, the transfer of traditional values appears as a mechanism of social development, where main characteristics of heredity and changeability are combined, i.e. the system homeostasis is being implemented.

The traditional society's person has his private interests. However, their expression is limited by the general sacred order, which tradition established. These restrictions may be imposed on the person directly or by means of his behaviour regulation by particular do's and don'ts. They establish some standard forms of personal identity and associations with each other. In other words, the person of traditional society, whatever goals he pursues, above all things, is dealing with the maintenance of the general sacred order. This defines the person's immediate aims and the final meaning of his actions. Traditions determine the prospect for everyday success, become the initial and universal prerequisite for achieving

stable personal identity or recognized social status.

The behaviour of the modern “Western man” is determined by other guidelines. The immediate aims and the final meaning of his actions determine the success or failure in the market area. A rational action aimed at accommodation of his own interests with demand and supply behaviour on the market appears the initial and universal prerequisite for achieving his self-identity or social recognition. There are no other behaviour imperatives for him. The market doesn’t suggest specific do’s and don’ts. This creates fairly stable prerequisites for diluting rules of morality and legal provisions. For this reason, the man of West has no any standard forms of personal identity and social integration (Zinovyev A.A. 1990).

In both cases, the effective imperatives of behaviour provide the prospect for life success one way or another. However, this success is achieved based on different motivations, different discourses as special ideal types of social communication, which gives rise to significant differences in the structures of consciousness, models of everyday or specific behaviour.

Thus, the discourse of traditional society, above all things, puts an emphasis on the way leading to the goal. For the person of traditional society, the action method, its means, resources or forms, which gains the nature of sacred value for him, is important for him. That’s why he is guided by various maxims like “keep your head down”, “run with the crowd” or “behave yourself properly” in everyday life.

And vice versa, the discourse of modern Western man puts an emphasis on the very goals of action. For this reason, his life activities are determined by the maxims like “do business”, “make a mark in this world” or “be a useful member of society”, which may also relate to values of a sacred nature (Fedotova V.G. 2005).

5. Discussion

The search for this synthesis becomes the main problem of the development strategy of many countries, including Kazakhstan, since the disturbance of the balance between modernity and traditionalism leads to the failure of transformations and acute social conflicts.

It is found that when changing the country’s economic model from the raw materials to innovative basis, the person and his creative potential become the priority of the Kazakhstan society’s development.

It’s shown that enhancing the unity of the Kazakhstan nation at a new sweep of history involves solution of a number of urgent tasks, in particular, shaping general civil identity; forming modern autonomous machinery of the State; ensuring supremacy of law; industrialization and economic growth based on diversification; creating the nation of the common future;

Features of the Kazakhstan civilization are characterized, which result from the peculiarity of sociocultural traditions and include norms of social life, cultural values, and world-outlook principles;

The study of new social-cultural changes of the Kazakhstan society showed that its parameters are expressed by

- general world view (with preservation of specific and individual modifications);
- specific mindset ensuring self-identity at the level of a large social group (nation, super ethnos, civilization);
- geonatural specific nature of the territory of activity having an impact on the formation of people’s interaction means;
- a single available language as a necessary means of social communication and management, storage and exchange of information, transfer of social knowledge.

The analysis of these sociocultural parameters showed that mutual relations between Kazakhstan and other civilizations can be built based on three principles, which should define the rules of the modern geopolitical game in the world. They are succession, competition, mutual support.

The culture of Kazakhstan will bear any tests since long mutual relations with Indo-Iranian, Chinese, Byzantine, Arabic, Turkic, Mongolian, Slavic civilizations didn’t destroy it, but made it stronger. All that only strengthened the national spirit, melting and assimilating all valuable things in the furnace of original steppe traditions. The difference between nomadic and Eurasian culture is fairly conditional since once nomadic tribes lived in the territory of Eurasia, which gradually shifted to half-nomad and then – to sedentary life. These tribes’ traditions and customs consecrated by mythological symbolics are the basis of Kazakh culture.

Today it’s impossible to revive the traditional culture of nomads in detail, and it’s doubtful whether the people living today need it. However, it’s equally clear that light touching to it multiplies the power of the nation, and that’s why its cultural meaning is unfading. The self-consciousness of any nation starts with myth (fable, epic), which expresses people’s idea of the creation of the world from chaos, human origin and different stages of his life activities in emotional-rational, objective and subjective, natural and supernatural form.

The traditions of the Kazakh culture directly determine the nature and essence of the identity phenomenon, if we understand it as a stability of individual, sociocultural, national or civilizational parameters, their self-relation allowing answering the questions who am I and who are we.

Nation-wide (integrative) and national causes have an impact on the formation of Kazakh identity. For a poly-ethnic country, such as Kazakhstan, the elaboration of “Kazakh” national idea and over-zealous implementation, some extremely patriotic people insist on, may result in destructive processes.

Today the search request of national identity is also attributable to new social realities, establishing of the independence and sovereignty of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Further consolidation of the Kazakhstan nation is based on the need to realize and successfully meet new challenges. They are historical time acceleration, global demographic challenge, the threat to global food security, severe water shortage, global energy challenge, natural resources depletion, “third industrial revolution”, growing global social instability, the crisis of human values of our civilization, and the threat of a new world destabilization. Realizing and overcoming these challenges of modernity is possible based on

consolidating values, in particular, new Kazakh patriotism, equality of all citizens and people's unity.

The nation's self-identity involves recovering political, cultural, economic history. However, self-identity is, above all, a particular kind of cultural artifact since it involves historical forces, internal and external factors.

The shift to a new stage of democratization is possible only following a number of small liberal reforms in political and economic spheres, which can be inconsequential and of a partial nature. Nonetheless, they are designed to contribute to the gradual elimination of authoritarianism elements, diminishing the State's role and growing the importance of non-governmental organizations, establishing the civil society.

The experience of democracy formation in Russia, western and eastern societies shows that successful completion of democratic transformations requires fulfilling a number of generally accepted and additional conditions, among which the principle of procedure universality is the determining one. This will allow not only completing micro- and macroeconomic stabilization at minimum losses but also contributing to shaping self-action, economic and political involvement of citizens. The pursuit of this principle is a powerful stabilizing factor of social production and a guarantor of the main principles of democracy, rule of law.

While understanding the complicity and ambiguousness of sociopolitical and social cultural changes of post-Soviet transition societies, it's necessary to modernize society with particular emphasis on economic problems and development of integrative ideology designed to rally socium, realize itself as an integral whole, channeling social energy in the general direction. At this stage of society transformation, the use of single state ideology without due regard to the range of pressing issues is unacceptable. The nation-wide ideology should correspond not only to uniting of the new democratic Kazakh society but also become a step towards the nation's turning into a politically and historically capable integrity involved in the world political process.

6. Conclusions

The study of interrelations between Kazakhstan and other civilizations showed that sociocultural changes in the Republic require developing new values and goals of person's economic and political activity. These changes of an ideological nature prepare and legitimize changes in the political and economic institutions of the Kazakh society, as well as the actual process of new social institutions' formation. In doing so, the interaction of social spheres in the course of sociocultural transformations shows that each sphere develops following its own patterns, which can play the role of a driving link at a certain stage of society's development and then give this role to the patterns of another sphere.

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